

Studies on Thiazolidinones. Part-II.
Synthesis and Fungitoxicities of
Thiazolidinones, Thiohydantoin and their
Derivatives derived from Thiocarbohydrazide

BAMA K. GARNAIK and RAJANI K. BEHERA*

P. G. Department of Chemistry, Sambalpur University,
 Jyotivihar-768 019

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It has been observed that 4-thiazolidinones have significant therapeutic efficiency¹. Several thiazolidinone derivatives have been shown to exhibit fungicidal and bactericidal properties^{1,2}. Thiohydantoin³ have wide range of biological activities. So, it was thought of interest to synthesise some new thiazolidinone and thiohydantoin derivatives with a view to evaluate their antibacterial and antifungal activities.

The diarylidene derivative of thiocarbohydrazide (1) was condensed with monoacetic acid both in acetic acid and sodium acetate and in dry pyridine medium to furnish the thiazolidinones (2) and the thiohydantoin (4), respectively. These thiazolidinones and thiohydantoin with different aromatic aldehydes furnished the corresponding arylidene derivatives (3 and 5). The diarylidene compounds (1) were further subjected to cycloaddition with mercapto acetic acid in dry benzene to give the thiazolidinones (6) which on condensation with aromatic aldehydes in sodium acetate and acetic acid medium furnished the corresponding arylidene derivatives (7) (Scheme 1).

The thiazolidinone (2; Ar=C₆H₅) shows its absorptions at 1720 (C=O), 1610 (C=N) and 2930 (CH₂) and 2850 cm⁻¹ (methin C-H). The benzylidene thiazolidinone (3; Ar=Ar'=C₆H₅) shows bands at 1700 (C=O) and 2840 and 2810 cm⁻¹ (methin C-H). The bathochromic shift of the carbonyl absorption in the benzylidene derivative is due to the conjugation of the carbonyl group with the exocyclic carbon-carbon double bond. This has been observed in case of other thiazolidinones, thiohydantoin and their arylidene derivatives.

Fungicidal and bactericidal activities: The fungicidal activities of several representative compounds were evaluated against *T. mentagrophytes* and *A. niger* as the test fungi. Sadboudar's broth (peptone 10 g dm⁻³, dextrose 20 g dm⁻³, pH≈6) was used as the test medium. The compounds were dissolved in ethanol and the test solution (1 ml) of different strength was added to each tube containing an equal amount of the medium. Tubes were autoclaved at 15 psi for 15 min prior to inoculation with suitable species of fungus. After inoculation, the tubes were incubated at 26±2° for 7 days and vegetation growth recorded visually in each case. 3-(*p*-Chlorobenzylideneazirine-2)-4-thiazolidinone (2; Ar=*p*-ClC₆H₄) and 1,3-di(*p*-chloro-

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) NaOAc, EtOH, (ii) ClOH₃COOH, NaOAc, HOAc, (iii) Ar'CHO, HOAc, NaOAc, (iv) ClOH₃COOH, pyridine, (v) HSCH₂COOH, C₆H₆.

benzylideneamino)-5-(*p*-methoxybenzal)-2-thiohydantoin (5; Ar=*p*-ClC₆H₄, Ar'=*p*-OCH₃C₆H₄) were found to be most active against *A. niger* in a concentration of 25 μg cm⁻³. Thiran 75W, a commercial fungicide, showed maximum activity against *A. niger* in a concentration of 7.5 μg cm⁻³. The compounds were tested for antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *S. typhi* and *S. aureus*, using disk method⁴. None of the compounds showed encouraging bactericidal potency.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 521 spectrophotometer. Thiocarbohydrazide was prepared by the known method from hydrazine and carbon disulphide.

N¹,N⁵-Dibenzylidenethiocarbohydrazide (1; Ar=C₆H₅): A solution of thiocarbohydrazide (10.6 g) in hot water (25 ml) and glacial acetic acid (2 ml) was added to a solution of freshly distilled benzaldehyde (21.2 g) in ethanol (15 ml). The solution was refluxed with stirring for 1 h and cooled. The resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 202° (Found: S, 11.38. C₁₅H₁₄N₂S requires: S, 11.34%). Similarly the following compounds were prepared: **N¹,N⁵-di(*p*-methoxybenzylidene)thiocarbohydrazide (1; Ar=*p*-OCH₃C₆H₄), m.p. 205° (Found: S, 9.31. C₁₇H₁₈N₂O₂S requires: S, 9.36%); **N¹,N⁵-di(*p*-chlorobenzylidene)thiocarbo-****

NOTES

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Ar	Ar'	Arylidene thiazolidinones (3)		Arylidene thiohydantoin (5)		Arylidene thiazolidinones (7)	
		M.p. °C	S % : Found/Calcd.	M.p. °C	S % : Found/Calcd.	M.p. °C	S % : Found/Calcd.
Phenyl	Phenyl	—	—	196	7.78 (7.80)	205	15.81 (15.84)
Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	165	7.18 (7.28)	206	7.12 (7.28)	>250	14.38 (14.41)
Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	208	7.92 (7.20)	>250	7.24 (7.20)	>250	14.16 (14.22)
<i>p</i> -Anisyl	Phenyl	184	6.69 (6.81)	215	6.74 (6.81)	208	14.44 (14.41)
<i>p</i> -Anisyl	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	216	6.40 (6.43)	248	6.51 (6.43)	>250	13.20 (13.23)
<i>p</i> -Anisyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	>250	6.28 (6.34)	>250	6.26 (6.34)	>250	12.96 (13.06)
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Phenyl	200	7.21 (7.20)	286	7.19 (7.20)	244	14.08 (14.22)
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	231	6.40 (6.29)	241	6.37 (6.29)	>250	12.86 (13.06)
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	>250	6.11 (6.23)	>250	6.19 (6.23)	>250	13.01 (12.90)

hydrazide (1; Ar = *p*-ClC₆H₄), m.p. 210° (Found: S, 9.11. C₁₅H₁₃N₄Cl₂S requires: S, 9.16%).

3-Benzylideneamino-2-(benzylideneazine-2)-4-thiazolidinone (2; Ar = C₆H₅): A mixture of 1 (2.82 g, 0.01 mol), monochloroacetic acid (0.94 g, 0.01 mol), anhydrous sodium acetate (1 g) in acetic acid (25 ml) was heated under reflux for 5 h with occasional shaking. The excess acetic acid was distilled off and the reaction mixture poured into water. The resulting grey solid was filtered, washed several times with hot water and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 90° (Found: S, 9.90. C₁₇H₁₄N₄SO requires: S, 9.93%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 080, 3 060 (ArH), 2 930 (CH₂), 2 850 (=CH), 1 720 (C=O), 1 610 (C=N) and 851 cm⁻¹ (C=S). Similarly the following compounds were prepared: 2-(*p*-methoxybenzylideneazine-2)-3-(*p*-methoxybenzylideneamino)-4-thiazolidinone (2; Ar = *p*-OCH₃), m.p. 98° (Found: S, 8.46. C₁₉H₁₈N₄O₃S requires: S, 8.38%); 2-(*p*-chlorobenzylideneazine-2)-3-(*p*-chlorobenzylideneamino)-4-thiazolidinone (2; Ar = *p*-ClC₆H₄), m.p. 110° (Found: S, 8.41. C₁₇H₁₃N₄O₂SCl₂ requires: S, 8.18%).

1,3-Dibenzylideneamino-2-thiohydantoin (4; Ar = C₆H₅): A mixture of 1 (2.82 g) and monochloroacetic acid (0.94 g) was mixed with dry pyridine (15 ml) and warmed a little till an exothermic reaction took place. After cooling, the reaction mixture was treated with ethanol (10 ml) and refluxed for 2 h. The content was poured onto crushed ice and the resulting grey solid was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 120° (Found: S, 9.72. C₁₇H₁₄N₄SO requires: S, 9.93%). Similarly the following compounds were prepared: 1,3-di(*p*-methoxybenzylideneamino)-2-thiohydantoin (4; Ar = *p*-OCH₃C₆H₄), m.p. 164° (Found: S, 8.51. C₁₉H₁₈N₄O₃S requires: S, 8.38%); 1,3-di(*p*-chlorobenzylideneamino)-2-thiohydantoin (4; Ar = *p*-ClC₆H₄), m.p. 130° (Found: S, 8.11. C₁₇H₁₃N₄SOCl₂ requires: S, 8.18%).

N¹,N⁵-Di(2-phenyl-4-oxothiazolidin-3-yl)thiourea (6; Ar = C₆H₅): A mixture of 1 (2.82 g), thioglycolic acid (1.84 g) in dry xylene (25 ml) was refluxed for 8 h using Dean-Stark apparatus. The excess xylene was distilled off and cooled. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 114° (Found: S, 22.36. C₁₉H₁₈N₄S₃O₂ requires: S, 22.32%). Similarly the following compounds were prepared: N¹,N⁵-di(2-*p*-methoxyphenyl-4-oxothiazolidin-3-yl)thiourea (6; Ar = *p*-OCH₃C₆H₄), m.p. 125° (Found: S, 19.50. C₂₁H₂₂N₄S₃O₄ requires: S, 19.59%); N¹,N⁵-di(2-*p*-chlorophenyl-4-oxothiazolidin-3-yl)thiourea (6; Ar = *p*-ClC₆H₄), m.p. 162° (Found: S, 18.99. C₁₉H₁₆N₄S₃O₂Cl₂ requires: S, 19.24%).

5-Benzal-3-benzylideneamino-2-(benzylideneazine-2)-4-thiazolidinone (3; Ar = Ar' = C₆H₅): A mixture of 6 (3.22 g), benzaldehyde (1.06 g) and sodium acetate (0.5 g) in glacial acetic acid (15 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture after cooling was poured onto crushed ice. The resulting yellow solid was filtered, washed several times with hot water, dried and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 167° (Found: S, 7.73. C₂₄H₁₈N₄SO requires: S, 7.80%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 2 840, 2 810 (=CH), 1 700 (C=O), 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

The physical and analytical data of the other arylidene thiazolidinones and arylidene thiohydantoin are presented in Table I.

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A Triterpene from *Salvia leucantha* Cav.

K. S. MUKHERJEE*, C. K. CHAKRAVORTY,

T. P. CHATTERJEE

and

P. BHATTACHARJEE

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati University,
Santiniketan-731 235

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In our previous communications^{1,2} we reported the isolation and characterisation of some triterpenes from the whole plant (aerial parts and roots) of *Salvia leucantha* Cav.³ We report herein the isolation and structure elucidation of a pentacyclic triterpene from the chloroform extract of the whole plant of *S. leucantha*.

The air-dried powdered whole plant (aerial parts and roots) of *S. leucantha* was successively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°), benzene and chloroform. The concentrated chloroform extract was subjected to chromatographic analysis over silica gel, elution being carried out with solvents of increasing polarity. Elution of the column with benzene afforded a solid, C₃₀H₅₀O₂, m.p. 205–7°, [α]_D²⁵ +65° (CHCl₃), crystallised from chloroform–benzene (1 : 2) mixture which formed an amorphous diacetate, C₃₄H₅₄O₄ on acetylation with acetic anhydride and pyridine at room temperature. This suggests that both the oxygen atoms in the triterpene are present as hydroxyl functions. The ¹H nmr spectrum (100 MHz, CDCl₃) of the triterpene showed resonances for five tertiary methyls at δ 0.74 (3H, s), 0.80 (3H, s), 0.96 (9H, s), two secondary methyls as doublets around δ 1.08 (6H, J 6 Hz), two hydroxy methyl (CH₂OH) at δ 3.25 and 3.60 (each 1H, d, J 10 Hz), one triplet around δ 4.52 (CHOH) and one vinylic proton at δ 5.15 (1H, m). The data suggest that the compound is an ursene type of triterpene with one secondary and one primary hydroxyl group. The mass spectral analysis is also consistent with the above view. The mass fragmentation pattern is typical of urs-12-ene type⁴ of pentacyclic triterpene and showed significant peaks at *m/z* 442 (M⁺),

411 (M⁺–CH₂OH), 234 (base peak), 207 (r.D.A. fragmentation around ring C), 203 (234–CH₂OH), 189 (207–H₂O) and 133. From the above fragmentation pattern it is evident that the secondary hydroxyl group of the triterpene is present in the A/B ring portion while the primary hydroxyl group is located in the D/E ring portion.

Finally, conversion of the triterpene to ursonic acid, m.p. 270–74°, [α]_D²⁵ +75° (CHCl₃) and methyl ursonate, m.p. 190°, [α]_D²⁵ +80° (CHCl₃) by chromic acid oxidation in glacial acetic acid followed by methylation with diazomethane completely elaborates its structure as urs-12-en-3,28-diol. Conclusive evidence in favour of the axial (α) orientation of C₃-hydroxyl group was obtained from ¹H nmr spectral data. The ¹H nmr spectrum of the triterpene showed a triplet-like signal of a single proton at δ 4.52 which shifts to δ 5.40 with a splitting pattern typical of 3α-acetoxy group⁵ in the spectrum of the diacetate.

All the above data as well as the comparison of the physical properties of uvaol (lit. m.p. 232°) and its diacetate (lit. m.p. 157–59°) reveal that the triterpene may be represented as 3-epi uvaol (1)⁶, and incidentally this is the first time isolation of this triterpene from plant origin.

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